

GAME-BASED METHODOLOGIES AIMED AT SEARCHING FOR NEW FORMS OF RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article examines current issues related to the introduction of creative teaching methods into the educational process. This naturally necessitates changes in the methods and forms of organizing the educational process. The creative process includes, first of all, the discovery of something new: new objects, new knowledge, new problems, new methods for solving them.*

Keywords: *implementation, interactive methods, educational process, education, game-based technologies.*

The education system requires significant changes in its content. Integrating creative teaching methods into the educational process is considered a critical task in modern times. This naturally necessitates changes in the methods and forms of organizing the learning process. Creativity involves, first and foremost, discovering the new: new objects, new knowledge, new problems, and new methods for solving them.

Recently, pedagogy, like many other scientific fields, has been undergoing a transformation in practices and methodologies. Business games, in particular, have gained widespread popularity. The implementation of game-based methodologies is directly linked to several broader processes aimed at searching for new forms of social organization and cultural relationships between teachers and students. According to L.S. Vygotsky, teaching is effective only when it fosters development. It stimulates and brings to life a range of functions that are in the process of maturing and lie within the zone of proximal development.

The new 21st century, along with the last decades of the 20th century, is characterized by an increasing demand for qualities such as the ability to act independently and actively, make decisions, and adapt to changing life conditions. Consequently, the priority in the education system has shifted from teaching activities to learning activities. In traditional education, the teacher acts as the main source of knowledge and controls the learning process. However, in personality-oriented education, the teacher serves as an organizer of independent and active cognitive activities of students and a consultant for their learning processes. Active and independent cognitive activities of students can be ensured through various educational technologies, such as small group learning, interactive methods, distance learning, project-based learning, and others.

Engaging students in active educational and cognitive activities during the learning process using specific methods and techniques is collectively referred to as *active teaching methods*.

Active teaching methods are ways of activating the educational and cognitive activities of students, encouraging them to engage in active intellectual and practical activities while mastering material [10]. Active teaching methods aim at students independently acquiring knowledge through active cognitive efforts.

In the learning process, active teaching methods are employed in the form of interactive teaching methods. These include discussions, brainstorming, round tables, case methods, business games, and more. Discussion, as a teaching method, involves discussing theoretical questions from the curriculum. It usually begins with stimulating questions and proposed solutions that have been prepared in advance. This method is often used in seminars and practical lessons. The brainstorming method involves specialists finding answers to complex problems by intensively expressing all possible ideas and suggestions that come to mind. In this process, no expressed idea is questioned or criticized, ensuring complete freedom for proposing any ideas. A round table is organized to enhance the understanding of theoretical problems by examining them from various scientific perspectives with the participation of specialists from different profiles and fields of activity [14]. One of the most effective and widespread methods of organizing active cognitive activities among students is the “**case method**”. Students are tasked with analyzing a real-life situation that simultaneously reflects a practical problem and highlights a set of knowledge they need to master to solve the problem. Importantly, the problem does not have definitive solutions. Situations may be presented in the form of descriptions, videos, and so on. The case method offers extensive educational opportunities. The variety of outcomes achieved through this method can be categorized into two groups: **Learning outcomes** related to mastering knowledge and skills (e.g., acquiring new information, learning data collection methods, mastering analysis techniques, etc.). **Educational outcomes** created by the participants themselves, such as achieving personal learning goals (e.g., improving professional competencies, gaining experience in decision-making, responding to new situations, solving problems, and more) [15]. Widely disseminating highly effective educational technologies, enhancing the role and improving the possibilities of active forms of learning, and independent problem solving by students is a common task of optimizing the educational process.

The unique nature of games lies in their heuristic quality—a spirit of creativity that pervades all unfolding actions. The outcomes of games are initially unpredictable and probabilistic, which lends them a distinctive, emotionally compelling charm that is familiar yet never exactly reproducible. The classification of methods proposed by A.M. Smolkin distinguishes between simulation-based methods of active and interactive learning, i.e., forms of lessons where cognitive activities mimic professional practices. All other methods are categorized as non-simulation-based and involve ways to activate cognitive engagement during lectures [10].

One of the most effective active learning methods is business games. In 1932, M.M. Birshteyn in Leningrad first employed game-based methods (business games) in education.

The pedagogical essence of business games lies in activating students' thinking, increasing their independence as future professionals, introducing a spirit of creativity in education, orienting it toward professional training, and preparing students for practical professional activities.

Currently, there are three spheres of application for game-based methods:

1. **Educational sphere:** Game methods are used in educational programs for training and professional development.
2. **Research sphere:** Games are employed for simulating future professional activities to study decision-making processes, assess the efficiency of organizational structures, etc.
3. **Production sphere:** Game methods are used to analyze specific system components and develop various elements of educational systems [8].

In preparing and conducting business games, every participant should have opportunities for self-assertion and self-development. The teacher should help students become the person they aspire to be in the game, revealing their best qualities during interactions.

Another highly effective innovative method is working in small groups. Small group work is a popular strategy because it allows all students to participate, practice collaboration, and develop interpersonal skills (e.g., active listening, forming consensus, resolving disagreements). These outcomes are less achievable in large groups. Small group work is integral to many interactive methods such as mosaics, debates, public hearings, simulations, mock trials, and more.

In organizing the educational process based on pedagogical technologies, the highest qualifications are required during the design phase, where a team of leading pedagogical methodologists develops instructional materials guided by didactic principles and the systemic approach of pedagogical technology. Thus, incorporating active and interactive forms and methods in teaching fosters student agency, encouraging self-realization, engagement, and interest in their future profession. Students reflect on the value of their activities, leading to significant changes in communication. This is manifested through sincerity, openness, independent judgments, autonomous evaluations, initiative, and leadership abilities.

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